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“A SILENT HERO”

In a far-flung Barangay, so remote and small,
He walks each day to heed education's call.
A teacher, yes, but so much more than this—
A parent, a sibling, a source of pure bliss.

He mends the wounds and dries the tears,
A doctor, a nurse calming childhood fears.
An engineer who builds, an attorney who defends,
A father and mother, a guide on whom each child depends.

His meager salary, barely his own,
He spends for school supplies, for children to have grown.
Rebuilding their homes, feeding their plight,
Clothing the needy in the darkest of night.

His own family, often left alone,
As he tends to the young, from dawn 'til he's home.
No time for laughter, no time to play,
For his pupils' future, he gives his day.

For the common good, his heart beats strong,
Yet misunderstood, and they claim him wrong.
The government, the authorities, turns a blind eye,
While he serves with passion, though he questions why.

A silent hero, in a world so unfair,
He carries the weight with love and care.
Though wronged and forgotten by buds and brethren,
He teaches on, fueled by love from heart within.